

The Coupling Constant Series and Nature of the Electron – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework, 8T, and the insights gain regarding the nature of the electron as the majestic (3) in the coupling term describing the Electric, it is possible to reason for the electron behavior around the hadron nuclei due to its numerical trait and his bounding to the nuclei via orbitals. Analysis of the Electron behavior will be made using a varying Lorentz manifold , $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected Einstein manifold, invoked stationary , $M = M_0 \times R,$ by the Euler Lagrange operator. The main tool of analysis is the primordial coupling constant series, derived in March 2021.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$(1):(30):(128):(850):(9254) \dots$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Examine the term describing the electric coupling. We proved majestic (3) is the electron in the 8-Theory thesis.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + 5 \quad (2.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (2.32)$$

What can be derived about the nature of the electron using the coupling constant representation? First of all, it is bounded by the bracket, it cannot escape and behave as the net variation, i.e. the photon. Despite the fact that both elements represented by a prime. Second, the electron is represented as a prime number, (3), which cannot vanish into matter, but also cannot propagate as a bosonic fields across the matrix its behavior than would propagation across the nuclei, in agreement with current understanding about the probabilistic behavior of that particle. There is no data regarding the current position, momenta, orbitals, no physical data of any sort is manifested in the 8-theory. An additional way to analyze it is to say that the electron blends in the hadronic cluster, $[(24 * 5) + (3)]$. The hadronic cluster is closed and represented in a closed term within the bracket. The summation of the term is perfectly suitable to vanish into matter.

$$\frac{24 * N_V}{\text{mod}(6)} = 0; \quad (2.33)$$

$$N_V = 2V + 1; V \geq 1$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P}$$

We took modulo six as we have to varying elements, which create threefold combinations. So despite the 8T do not provide physical data of any sort, and it completely probabilistic as nature really is, it does provide beautiful insights regarding the process of propagation. First term from the left describe compact hadronic structure, the majestic (3) is a propagation of the electron across the nuclei, he is bound to it and can't escape. This factor than yields a net curvature on the manifold, which is a boson propagation, isomorphic to prime numbers or one for the strong interaction.